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Executive Summary

This document is prepared in the context of the COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE) project. This report presents the outcomes and insights derived from the second phase of the piloting activities. The primary aim of this piloting phase is to test the ERA Hubs definition in the two regions identified through the Call for Champions. To this end, this report presents the pilot regions and their use cases and puts forth the insights related to the testing of the ERA Hubs definitions and framework and its associated tools.

This information gathered in this report serves to further the understanding and testing of the ERA Hubs definition that is proposed as a part of the COOPERATE project in two further piloting **regions identified through the Call for Champions**, notably the Centre-Val de Loire region in France, and the Łódzkie region in Poland.

The use case related to the Centre-Val de Loire pilot region is centred on a thorough analysis of its renewable hydrogen ecosystem and involved in the hydrogen value chain of the region. As a transit region located in the middle of France, Centre-Val de Loire has a number of major logistics trade routes running through it, connecting heavy industry stakeholders, often situated in other regions. Due to this, the region has a unique opportunity to decarbonise a substantial amount of this traffic with its existing local expertise provided by a lively ecosystem of players across the quadruple helix. There are varying degrees of knowledge valorisation efforts targeted, depending on the actors and their position in the value chain. The activities are centred around the University of Orléans together with industry stakeholders. There is a clear interest and willingness to continue strengthening collaboration with academia and other stakeholders, thereby creating a small ecosystem involving industry, university and the region. Interaction and collaboration between the ecosystem actors seem to be present, but there is willingness to structure and foster this collaboration further.

For the Łódzkie region, the University of Lodz played a leading role by coordinating the participation. The circular economy ecosystem was the focus of the use case, whereby the predominating industry in Łódzkie was the textile industry until the 20th century, which then later collapsed to be replaced by other industries, including power, metallurgy, machinery, construction, pharmaceutical and agri-food. Now in the region, circular economy is dominated by topics related to natural resource availability related to lignite and waste generation and domestic material consumption. The University of Lodz plays a central role in coordinating the Forum Circulare ecosystem through its academic strengths and infrastructures – such as the Centre for Sustainable Development – to actively engage local stakeholders. Initiatives led by the university and its partners align with broader national energy security goals include, among others, joint projects with businesses and public authorities, demonstrating that initial coordination mechanisms are in place in the Łódzkie region. These efforts show that there is a strong basis for scaling up circular economy initiatives and integrating a regional innovation system.

These use cases and case studies shed light on the way in which collaboration in ecosystems is structured towards knowledge valorisation, highlighting some challenges and priorities among them. Notable among them are governance mechanisms to foster collaboration, including clear policy and strategy guidance to enable ecosystems and value chains, as well as access to innovation support and funding, and weak collaboration with civil society.

These aspects are scheduled to be further discussed at the COOPERATE Co-creation session in May 2025, where the monitoring framework and policy recommendations will be discussed together with the testing of the tools arising from COOPERATE including the COOPERATE Self-Assessment (SELF-ASSESSMENT), the COOPERATE Playbook (PLAYBOOK) and COOPERATE Toolbox (TOOLBOX), which were developed to assess and help progress the maturity of Regional & Innovation (R&I) ecosystems.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EIS	European Innovation Scoreboard
ERA	European Research Area
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RIS	European Regional Innovation Scoreboard
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

This document is prepared in the context of the COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE) project. This report presents the outcomes and insights derived from the second phase of the piloting activities. The primary aim of this piloting phase is to test the ERA Hubs definition in the two regions identified through the Call for Champions. To this end, this report presents the pilot regions and their use cases and puts forth the insights related to the testing of the ERA Hubs definitions and framework and its associated tools.

This report is structured as follows:

- The first chapter provides information **about the project**, the **purpose** of the piloting activities and the **methodology** applied throughout the piloting phases in order to maximise the outputs towards the project objectives
- The second chapter focuses on the **piloting activities carried out in the regions identified through the Call for Champions**, notably the Centre-Val de Loire region in France, and the Łódzkie region in Poland. Details on the description of the activities carried out, as well as the ecosystem, main actors, level of maturity, challenges and priorities are outlined for each ecosystem.
- The third chapter outlines the **conclusions** and next steps towards the **finalisation** of the piloting phase in the context of the COOPERATE project.

2. Context and framework

COOPERATE is a Horizon Europe project that aims to develop and pilot the ERA Hub concept, hence implementing the first steps of the ERA Policy Action 15 “Building up research and innovation ecosystems to improve excellence and competitiveness”¹. Drawing on the successful experiences of the EuroTech Universities Alliance and their R&I ecosystems, the aim of the COOPERATE project is to create a methodology to support the creation and development of ERA Hubs and to set the basis for the creation of a pan-European network of ERA Hubs.

ERA hubs are a spearhead in the European Commission’s strategy to boost regional innovation in the European Research Area (ERA). The ERA Hubs could support organisations – and people – to bring together different stakeholders, join up public and private spheres and break existing silos.

COOPERATE’s overall objective is to develop and pilot the ERA Hub concept based on the vision and success stories developed within the EuroTech Universities Alliance and their R&I ecosystems. COOPERATE aims to facilitate the sharing of best practices across regions, promoting a more seamless and efficient research environment within the ERA Hubs network.

COOPERATE’s vision of ERA Hubs: An ERA Hub is an ecosystem of quadruple helix actors led by universities aiming at improving knowledge valorisation within their region.

Figure 1: ERA Hubs definition as developed by COOPERATE

An ERA Hub is an **ecosystem** of **quadruple helix actors** led by **universities** aiming at improving **knowledge valorisation** within their **region**

The ERA Hubs operate within their broader R&I regional ecosystems, which constitute the background conditions for knowledge valorisation

Source: COOPERATE project

To aid ecosystem players, COOPERATE offers a PLAYBOOK and a TOOLBOX. Its overarching aim is to **provide a framework for nurturing dynamic ecosystems** that stimulate research

¹ European Commission. (n.d.) European Research Area Platform: Amplifying access to research and innovation excellence across the Union. Retrieved from: <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024/amplifying-access-research-and-innovation-excellence-across-union>

excellence, attract and retain top talent, facilitate knowledge transfer, foster collaboration among diverse actors, secure adequate funding, establish effective governance structures, and foster a culture of innovation. The PLAYBOOK serves as the strategic foundation, describing hallmarks of excellence along the seven lines of action and providing a roadmap for ecosystem development. Based on these seven areas, the TOOLBOX offers 33 concrete, actionable tools that ecosystems can implement to elevate their maturity, tailored to their assessment results.

The **ERA-Hub Framework Model** has been tested and validated in two phases (see Figure 2):

- The first phase piloting has focused on the Czech, Dutch and Danish ecosystems. Feedback from these three ecosystems has supported the definition of the ERA Hubs concept and the design of the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX as well as the testing of the SELF-ASSESSMENT which feeds into the COOPERATE platform (PLATFORM) (see Figure 3).
- In the second phase, two additional ecosystems have been engaged through a Call for Champions, namely **France (Université d'Orléans)** and **Poland (University of Lodz)**. These ecosystems have benefitted from support to assess the level of maturity of the regional R&I ecosystem and identify needs related to fostering knowledge valorisation, while developing a 'use case' on the application of the ERA Hubs Framework. Ecosystems will also benefit from the opportunity to test the SELF-ASSESSMENT, and feedback on the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX in the May co-creation session dedicated to this aim.

Figure 2: Piloting phases in COOPERATE

Source: COOPERATE project

Figure 3: Recap of insights from phase I piloting: Denmark

Challenges found in the piloting activities in Lyngby's ecosystem (Denmark) based on testing of the COOPERATE Self Assessment Tool

Source: COOPERATE project

A **monitoring framework for ERA-Hubs**, complete with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been developed and validated. **Policy recommendations** will be made available in a White Book, considering various dimensions such as R&I ecosystem capacity building and talent mobility. These will be revisited in the forthcoming co-creation session with the phase 2 pilot regions.

3. Phase 2 piloting activities

The COOPERATE project constitutes an opportunity to co-design the European Research Area (ERA) Hub concept within various regional and thematic focal areas. The use cases identified in the first phase pilot as well as the second phase pilot present the opportunity to illustrate the application of the ERA Hubs framework, its challenges and possibilities. Furthermore, these use cases serve to test, validate and finetune the main dimensions (lines of action) of an ERA Hub, the core elements of the interaction within an ecosystem, as well as the interregional collaboration dynamics between ecosystems.

The overall approach for the phase two piloting activities builds upon the approach applied in the first phase pilot. Figure 4 presents the approach used for the piloting of the ERA Hubs framework and tools in the COOPERATE project. It consists of three main phases: it starts with a ‘discovery’ phase that allows to identify the main actors and dimensions of a given ecosystem through mapping exercises. In the second phase, the feedback from the actors regarding their needs and challenges for collaboration are gathered and analysed. The third phase focuses on testing the tools and identifying topics and needs for future policy recommendations.

Figure 4: Approach for Piloting ERA Hubs

Source: COOPERATE project.

The regions selected to test the ERA Hubs framework in the second phase of the piloting self-identify as emerging ecosystems according to the Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL) scheme as presented and interpreted in the Call for Champions and outlined in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Classification of ecosystems as applied in the Call for Champions

Non-existent	Emerging	Mature	Advanced
There is no or little interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation	There is some interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation but the coordination and development of joint activities is limited and requires further development.	There is interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation in the delivery of joint activities but there are major points requiring improvement	There is fluid interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation in the delivery of joint activities

Source: COOPERATE project.

are emerging (Łódzkie) and moderate (Centre-Val de Loire) innovators according to the European Regional Innovation Scoreboard (RIS)², and identify as emerging innovations as set out in requirements of the Call for Champions. The RIS provides an assessment of the relative research and innovation performance at regional level. The selected regions present, however, varying degrees of development and performance when looking at specific ecosystems (i.e. thematic-based ecosystems), each of them facing specific challenges and contexts. The use cases developed by the COOPERATE project therefore serve to test the applicability of the ERA Hubs framework and tools in a diversity of contexts.

The expected outcomes of the second phase piloting for the regional ecosystems included:

- An assessment of the maturity of the regional R&I ecosystem, strengths and areas of improvement related to the specific use case identified
- Identifying and linking with relevant actors to foster knowledge valorisation in the region
- Identifying common priorities and discussion on collaboration mechanisms to further foster the ecosystem
- Identifying common needs that could be addressed through public policy support.

At the same time, some **expected outcomes of the phase two piloting for the COOPERATE project** include:

- Fine-tuning of the **SELF-ASSESSMENT**, used to measure the maturity of the ecosystem,
- Providing inputs towards the **PLATFORM**,
- Supporting fine tuning the **PLAYBOOK** and **TOOLBOX**, where relevant, and
- Supporting in developing **policy recommendations** towards the future development of the ERA policy related to ERA Hubs related to the following underlying questions:
 - How to reinforce knowledge valorisation at the regional level?

² European Commission. (2023). Regional Innovation Scoreboard. Retrieved from: <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

- How to reinforce regional R&I ecosystems through ERA Hubs?
- How (and which) public policy support mechanisms can reinforce the university's role and activities in knowledge valorisation?

The following sub-chapters outline the specific use cases and narratives related to the two piloting regions involved in the phase two pilot, with the following overarching structure:

- Description of the activities carried out
- Description of the ecosystem
- Main actors involved
- Level of maturity
- Challenges
- Priorities

3.1 A focus on Centre-Val de Loire

3.1.1 Description of the activities carried out within the project

The ERA Hubs project's French pilot focused on the region of Centre-Val de Loire, conducting a thorough analysis of its renewable hydrogen ecosystem and involved in the hydrogen value chain of the region. The work was organised into stages, as follows (see also Figure 5):

- A kick-off was organised to agree on the objectives and action plan, while at the same time identifying common needs and priorities of the phase 2 pilot activities. This included identifying and laying the focus on the renewable hydrogen use case for the ecosystem.
- Building on this, information was collected by way of desk research, analysing policy documents, which was further complemented as the piloting continued.
- Interviews complemented the desk research, and took place in March and April of 2025, involving three public organisations, two stakeholders from academia, and four industry representatives. They provided insights into the inner mechanisms of the ecosystem, including their priorities and challenges, their ways of collaborating, as well as their analysis of the region's potential and future expectations and outlook. An emphasis was placed on the ecosystem's maturity regarding a potential application to the Clean Hydrogen Partnership's Hydrogen Valley project, discussing the needs and hindrances of the stakeholders.
- A workshop took place on 23 April, presenting the insights gathered from the data collection and analysis and summarising the position towards the Hydrogen Valleys call, while at the same time collecting the common understanding of challenges and priorities moving forward to advance the ecosystem and its collaboration around renewable hydrogen. The workshop included 38 registered participants, as follows:
 - 8 persons from companies developing hydrogen production projects
 - 5 persons from universities/research laboratories
 - 9 persons from local authorities (cities, departmental council, local community)
 - 1 person from transport company
 - 4 persons from federations/associations
 - 2 persons from energy specialist companies
 - 2 persons from industrial companies on the hydrogen value chain
 - 7 persons from the regional council
 - 2 persons from IDEA Consult
- A final co-creation session is scheduled in May 2025 to recap insights from the phase 1 pilot, test the PLAYBOOK, TOOLBOX and SELF-ASSESSMENT from COOPERATE and provide inputs to the monitoring framework and policy recommendations

Figure 5: Phase 2 piloting in Centre-Val de Loire

Centre Val de Loire : Focus on renewable hydrogen ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project

3.1.2 Description of the ecosystem

The Centre-Val de Loire region is situated in a land-locked region south of Paris (see Figure 6) and boasts 2,581,500 inhabitants and is one of the eighteen administrative regions of France, bordering six other regions. It comprises six departments in the middle of the Loire Valley and covers a total of 39,151km². It has a well-established logistics network with two international airports, nine highways, one TGV (inter-city high speed service) and 500 trains crossing the network daily. The region is located in a strategic position in central France and is particularly recognized in aeronautics, defence, agri-food, cosmetics, perfumes and health. It is the number one region in France for medicine and cosmetic production and the third for industrial jobs³. In 2023 the Regional Development Agency of Centre-Val de Loire supported 30 foreign investment projects totalling 2.5 million euros, thereby creating 1045 jobs.⁴

³ Dev'up (n.d.) Investment in the Loire Valley. Retrieved from: <https://www.devup-centrevalde Loire.fr/invest-in-loire-valley-region/>

⁴ Dev'up (2023) Centre-Val de Loire, a leading destination for businesses with foreign capital. Retrieved from: <https://www.devup-centrevalde Loire.fr/wp-content/uploads/foreign-investments.pdf>

Figure 6: Centre-Val de Loire location

Source: Dev'Up Centre-Val de Loire

The renewable hydrogen ecosystem in the region has as an underlying policy document a roadmap for the development of green hydrogen in the Centre-Val de Loire region⁵, which relates to a regional scheme in France for the sustainable development of regions⁶.

As a transit region located in the middle of France, Centre-Val de Loire has a number of major logistics trade routes running through it, connecting heavy industry stakeholders, often situated in other regions. Due to this, the region has a unique opportunity to decarbonise a substantial amount of this traffic with its existing local expertise provided by a lively ecosystem of players across the quadruple helix (see Figure 7). The technological priorities can be centred around mobility, involving the retrofitting of coaches, Internal Combustion Engine (ICE), small and light trucks, medium-duty and heavy-duty trucks, as well as the development of an electrolysis pilot facility.

⁵ Région Centre-Val de Loire (2020) Rapport du Président du Conseil Régional à la session Plénière du 18 février 2020 REGION 100% RENOUEVABLE: UNE FEUILLE DE ROUTE POUR LE DÉVELOPPEMENT DE L'HYDROGÈNE VERT EN CENTRE-VAL DE LOIRE

⁶ SRADDET <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/sraddet-schema-strategique-prescriptif-integrateur-regions>

Figure 7: Example of stakeholder network related to the use of renewable hydrogen and ICE

Source: Region Centre-Val de Loire

3.1.3 Main actors involved

In the Centre-Val de Loire region, industry stakeholders, public institutions, universities and civil communities all play an important role in shaping the local renewable hydrogen ecosystem (see Figure 8). It includes the regional authority, university and industry showcasing a good collaboration effort enabled by physical and perceived proximity. This building upon a strong renewable hydrogen value chain understanding in the region (see also Figure 9), with a clear view on actors in play.

There are varying degrees of **knowledge valorisation** efforts targeted, depending on the actors and their position in the value chain. The activities are centred around the University of Orléans together with industry stakeholders. There is a clear interest and willingness to continue strengthening collaboration with academia and other stakeholders, thereby creating a small ecosystem involving industry, university and the region. In order for this to manifest, there is a need to ensure the funding of both fundamental research and high TRL level, market-ready projects.

The region has also initiated a Working Group, bringing together various local stakeholders to explore several potential uses and benefits of hydrogen. Among these are the decarbonisation of the tourism sector, as it is especially successful along the Loire Valley castles, as well as the possibility of decarbonising local industries such as glassmaking and paper manufacturing⁷.

⁷ COOPERATE Project. (n.d.). COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production: Call for champions, Annex I. Centre-Val de Loire region.

Figure 8: Actors involved in the Centre-Val de Loire renewable hydrogen ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project

Figure 9: The hydrogen value chain in the Centre-Val de Loire region

Source: Dev'Up 2024

3.1.4 Level of maturity

The Centre-Val de Loire region is classified as a Moderate Innovator in the 2023 Regional Innovation Scoreboard, with the innovation performance decreased by 5.4% since 2016. According to the RIS the region shows relative strength in comparison to France and the EU average in digital skills but lags behind in trademark applications. The data further highlights possible structural differences, such as an above EU average employment in manufacturing and a below EU average population density⁸.

In their Call for Champions application the region self-identifies as an emerging ecosystem, wherein their application shows a burgeoning activity in terms of new initiatives having been recently launched or with potential to be developed in the short term.

The University of Orleans is recognized nationally and internationally for its advanced research on combustion in internal combustion engines, specialising in the combustion of hydrogen, ammonia and methanol. These are promising fuels for decarbonising heavy transport, maritime industry, rail industry, and agriculture. The university has numerous collaborations with industry stakeholders including a number of joint laboratories.

Interaction and collaboration between the ecosystem actors seem to be present, but there is willingness to structure and foster this collaboration further. In terms of the degree of maturity of the collaboration across actors in this ecosystem, several examples can be highlighted:

- **Partnerships:** There are increasing collaborations between universities and industries, particularly in joint laboratories for research projects with Stellantis, Phinia, or Eurenco.
- **Hydrogen Valleys:** The University of Orleans is involved in one of the two awarded valleys in France, the AdvancedH2Valley project⁹ led by Lhyfe.
- **Networking Events:** The Centre-Val de Loire regional government has organised a Working Group, to bring together stakeholders from various sides of the hydrogen ecosystem to work together towards a possible Hydrogen Valley project, as well as a yearly Hydrogen Days event with an average of 350 participants consisting of presentations, roundtable discussions, and networking opportunities.

The call for Hydrogen Valleys under the Clean Hydrogen Partnership presents an opportunity for the region to showcase its abilities and further foster the ecosystem by creating a so-called *hydrogen valley* in the territory. Information on the call is included in Figure 10. Several working group meetings to date have focussed on the exploration of this opportunity, and part of assessing the maturity of this ecosystem has been centred on assessing specific the maturity towards this concrete opportunity.

⁸ European Commission (2023) Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2023 Regional Profiles France. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ris/2023/ec_rtd_ris-regional-profiles-france.pdf

⁹ AdvancedH2Valley (2024) AdvancedH2Valley: Showcasing Advanced Hydrogen Valley in Western France Retrieved from: <https://www.advancedh2valley.eu/>

In terms of concrete positioning towards the opportunity, the data collection has shown that while there are several interesting examples of hydrogen valleys to work from, including those from within and outside of France, the ecosystem is not ready to position itself towards the call yet. An action plan with clear milestones would benefit the development of a common vision towards developing a hydrogen valley building on three pillars of policy, intra and interregional collaboration and funding of demonstration and piloting.

Figure 10: Clean Hydrogen Partnership information

The Clean Hydrogen Partnership launched its new call for proposals in January 2025, with a budget of € 184.5 million for projects to support the creation of cutting-edge hydrogen technologies. 80M€ of this funding will be made available for the creation and support of large and small-scale Hydrogen Valleys. It aims to demonstrate an ecosystem built on the complete value chain of hydrogen to foster the emergence of the widest possible array of valleys configurations. France has a large-scale valley in the region of Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (IMAGHyNE) and a small scale in the Pays de la Loire region that have been awarded already (AdvancedH2Valley).

Source: Hydrogen Valleys - Clean Hydrogen Partnership¹⁰

3.1.5 Challenges

There are several challenges currently faced by the renewable hydrogen ecosystem in Centre-Val de Loire, several of which have been touched upon in the preceding sections and are summarised in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Challenges related to the ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project

The unifying thread running through all the interviews that have been conducted has been the issue of **high costs**. The price of hydrogen is expensive already and running costs are disproportionately high as well, so the initial investment and everyday usage costs are perceived as too high to be considered competitive.

¹⁰ Clean Hydrogen Partnership (n.d.) Hydrogen Valleys. Retrieved from: https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/get-involved/hydrogen-valleys_en

Another challenge to consider is the **limited demand** in the region. Due to a limited presence of heavy industry, developing ecosystems are having trouble relying on local uptake of their produced hydrogen, resulting in a turn towards mobility instead of heavy industry. Generally, it can be said that too many actors would like to produce and distribute, with not enough demand, which hinders the capacity to collaborate further.

The **landlocked**, rural nature of Centre-Val de Loire is also a barrier, as there is no demand coming from seaports or shipping related industries, which are traditionally large users of hydrogen-based solutions. The region also lacks urban density and does not have enough major cities with large industries present, which could explain the consumption market and limited demand issue mentioned above.

The final challenge coming up in the majority of stakeholder interviews has been a **limited policy orientation** where **momentum** for hydrogen, as policymaking and ambition has slowed since its initial popularity at the time when the roadmap¹¹ was developed. There is a lack of unified, updated strategy largely at French national level as well as regional level, that would help in guiding stakeholders where to focus their efforts, in addition to protecting them from competition outside of Europe.

3.1.6 Priorities

Resulting from the data collection, including the considerations from the discussions during the workshop, the priorities for further enhancing the knowledge valorisation coming from the Centre-Val de Loire renewable hydrogen ecosystem can be summarised according to three main areas (see Figure 12):

- Clear policy signal related to hydrogen and underlying technologies
- Intra and interregional collaboration to serve as an opportunity to develop the ecosystem further through best practices, knowledge exchange and even interregional innovation
- Funding for demonstration and piloting would allow to showcase capabilities, strengthen and grow them towards a hydrogen valley in a certain geographic domain

To enhance knowledge valorisation within the ecosystem, actions towards fostering mobility could be considered. Collaboration could further be supported through incentives such as investments to foster the creation of hydrogen demand, for example in relation to hydrogen vehicles or other structured collaboration projects.

¹¹ Région Centre-Val de Loire (2020) Rapport du Président du Conseil Régional à la session Plénière du 18 février 2020 REGION 100% RENOUVELABLE: UNE FEUILLE DE ROUTE POUR LE DÉVELOPPEMENT DE L'HYDROGÈNE VERT EN CENTRE-VAL DE LOIRE

Figure 12: Priorities resulting from the analysis

Source: COOPERATE project

Within the ecosystem, it would be beneficial to continue **fostering exchange**, for example by the elaboration of concrete Action Plans to identify focus areas and foster a unified approach. A possible suggestion could be the development of semi-centralised production hubs for the region, targeting mobility, that would answer to local demand and would be able to export the surplus using trucks instead of hydrogen infrastructures. Intra and Interregional collaboration would also be important to foster, identifying collaboration potentials with other similar regions either within France or Europe, whereby the Hydrogen Valleys Partnership¹² which the region is already a part of can present a further opportunity to capitalise upon.

An essential stepping stone to the development of a Hydrogen Valley would be **pilot plants and demonstration activities**, taking into account geographic considerations, that would be able to perform a good evaluation of the ecosystem on a smaller scale. It would be important to have continuous funding to incentivise further structured collaboration towards common goals. Subsidies could also be instrumental in fostering the business model related to the demonstration of mobility solutions, for example a grant subsidies model that would enable the funding of private vehicles being retrofitted, thereby creating demand.

¹² European Commission (n.d.) Hydrogen Valleys S3 Partnership. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/communities-and-networks/s3-community-of-practice/partnership_industrial_mod_hydrogen_valleys_en

3.2 A focus on the Łódzkie region

3.2.1 Description of the activities carried out within the project

As part of the piloting of the ERA Hubs in Poland, a mapping and an analysis of the circular economy ecosystem in the Łódzkie region was conducted. A central component of this effort involved conducting a series of in-depth interviews with key stakeholders actively engaged in or influencing the regional circular economy landscape. These included representatives from inter-municipal associations, academic institutions, non-governmental organisations and research associations.

The interviews provided valuable qualitative insights into the roles, priorities, challenges, and perspectives of various actors within the regional ecosystem. Stakeholders shared their experiences with knowledge valorisation, collaborative efforts, and implementation of circular economy principles across different sectors.

In addition to interviews, broader contextual information, such as insights from relevant policy documents, available statistical data, and ongoing initiatives (e.g., EU-funded projects such as the FRONTSH1P project) was used to understand the region’s progress toward circularity and how different stakeholders collaborate, align their efforts, and contribute to shared objectives. These elements helped to establish a foundation for analysing the development of the circular economy ecosystem, including collaboration dynamics and key enablers and barriers.

Figure 13: Overview of the piloting activities in the Łódzkie region

Łódzkie Region: Focus on the circular economy ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project

3.2.2 Description of the ecosystem

The ERA Hubs pilot in Poland was based on an analysis of the circular economy ecosystem in the Łódzkie region. This region was selected through the Call for Champions, a process in which the University of Lodz played a leading role by coordinating and submitting the application.

The region is also involved in the ongoing FRONTSH1P project (Box 1)¹³; the following paragraph includes information taken from the project report regarding the circular economy ecosystem of the region.

Figure 14: Łódzkie region

Source: Source: Łódzkie Region – Multimedial Poland. (n.d.). [Photograph of Łódzkie region]. Polska Multimedialn

The region is home to 2,426,806 inhabitants, comprising 21 counties and 177 municipalities, which include a total of 527 cities and 4465 villages¹⁴.

In the region there is a total of approximately 5,800 NGOs, with most of them registered as associations and foundations. Compared to other Polish regions, Łódzkie has a larger number of NGOs focused on supporting local and socio-economic development – although the majority operates in areas such as sport, tourism, hobbies and recreational activities¹⁵.

Regarding the region's circular economy ecosystem, the predominating industry in Łódzkie was the textile industry until the 20th century, which then later collapsed to be replaced by other industries, including power, metallurgy, machinery, construction, pharmaceutical and agri-food¹⁶. Now in the region, the following indicators stand out when it comes to moving toward a circular economy:

- Natural resource availability: the region has a high availability of natural resources, with over 30 tonnes domestic extraction per capita in this region. A major part of this comes from lignite, with the Bełchatów mine supplying about half of Poland's lignite needs.
- Waste generation and domestic material consumption: by comparing how much waste is produced with the amount of materials consumed, the Łódzkie region is efficient in

¹³ FRONTSH1P (2022) Policy Framework and Market analysis – POLICY

¹⁴ FRONTSH1P (2022) Policy Framework and Market analysis – POLICY

¹⁵ idem

¹⁶ idem

terms of resource use, with this indicator being 7-10%¹⁷. A big part of this progress is thanks to higher recycling rates and more efficient resource use.

Box 1: FRONTSH1P Project

FRONTSH1P Project insights (FRONTrunner approach to Systemic circular, Holistic & Inclusive solutions for a new Paradigm of territorial circular economy)

The FRONTSH1P Project in the Polish region of Łódzkie aims at supporting a green and fair transition in the region by demonstrating four circular economy models that transform waste into useful resources. The goal is to help reduce emissions, improve the quality of life and connect urban and rural areas through innovative circular solutions.

FRONTSH1P brings together multiple key regional players, including local authorities, research institutions, civil society and businesses. These actors work together to find a circular economy strategy that includes common targets and monitoring methods. Actions include:

- Identifying existing circular initiatives and policies
- Sharing best practices and solutions
- Creating links between universities, companies and citizens
- Building a clear strategy with measurable goals

The project – and the related research behind it – supports the creation of a Circular Regional Cluster. It focuses on how to govern the cluster effectively, considering legal barriers, market challenges, and the existing policy landscape at all levels. It also explores ideas for circular public procurement and ways to improve investment flows and data sharing. The study recommends a governance model built on cooperation between 4 stakeholder groups: businesses, academia, society and government – with local authorities playing a key role in coordinating efforts.

Source: FRONTSH1P (2022) Policy Framework and Market analysis – POLICY

¹⁷ idem

3.2.3 Main actors involved

The University of Lodz applied to the call for Champions on behalf of the Łódzkie region, which later listed the following actors involved in shaping the regions' circular economy ecosystem as shown below including universities, industries, civil society organisations, national, regional and local governments¹⁸.

¹⁸ COOPERATE Project. (n.d.). COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production: Call for champions, Annex I. Łódzkie region.

Figure 15: Actors involved in Łódzkie circular economy ecosystem

Source: COOPERATE project.

After a follow-up call with the University of Lodz, the contacts shown in Figure 15 were identified and provided by the university. These people were subsequently approached and interviewed during the next stages of the process (Table 2:).

Table 2: List of institutions interviewed

Institution
ZM Bzura <i>Coalition of 19 municipalities in the Łódzkie region established in 2009. Its mission is to develop and implement a comprehensive municipal waste management system</i>
Horizon Europe Contact Point
University of Lodz <i>Lodz University is the major university in the region and one of the largest in Poland. It is strongly focused on research and international cooperation.</i>
ERSA – The European Regional Science Association Polish section <i>The association brings together scholars and practitioners focused on regional development, spatial planning, and regional policy in Poland</i>
OPUS Centre, non-governmental organisation <i>The centre is dedicated to supporting civil society, social innovation, and community development initiatives in Poland</i>
Parzęczew <i>Municipality part of the Łódzkie region with 914 inhabitants</i>
Kflex, company, leader <i>International manufacturer specialising in flexible thermal and acoustic insulation materials</i>

Source: COOPERATE project.

3.2.4 Level of maturity

The Łódzkie region classifies itself as an Emerging Innovator in their application to the call for Champions¹⁹. This is also confirmed in the 2024 Regional Innovation Scoreboard, with an overall regional performance that is below 70% compared to the EU average. These results can be justified by how the region performs weakly in indicators such as R&D expenditures in both public and private sectors, public-private co-publications and international scientific collaboration. The region also lags behind with digital skills, employment in knowledge-intensive activities and the proportion of innovative enterprises. However, the region performs well in other areas, such as employment in agriculture and mining²⁰.

¹⁹ COOPERATE Project. (n.d.). COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as in Ter- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production: Call for champions, Annex I. Łódzkie region.

²⁰ European Commission. (2024). Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2024: Łódzkie (PL71). European Union. Retrieved from: https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/PL?region=PL71&perf_indicators=1

However, based on the information provided in the Call for Champions, the region holds potential in acting as a coordinator in the transition towards a more circular and innovation-oriented economy. The University of Lodz plays a central role in coordinating the *Forum Circulare* ecosystem through its academic strengths and infrastructures – such as the Centre for Sustainable Development – to actively engage local stakeholders. Its development focuses on three interlinked areas: circular communities, energy independence and security, and sustainable entrepreneurship. In addition, initiatives led by the university and its partners, such as the installation of a photovoltaic farm and advisory work on establishing municipal energy cooperatives, align with broader national energy security goals. These projects support the region’s role in implementing the Territorial Plan for Just Transition, which includes up to 35 communes in Łódzkie. Additionally, ongoing cooperation with NGOs, such as Art_Incubator, Skyhub and OPUS, as well as joint projects with businesses and public authorities, demonstrate that initial coordination mechanisms are in place in the Łódzkie region. These efforts show that there is a strong basis for scaling up circular economy initiatives and integrating a regional innovation system²¹.

3.2.5 Challenges

Both the desk research and interviews conducted as part of the analysis of the circular economy ecosystem in the Łódzkie region point to a number of persistent challenges that hinder progress in implementing circular economy practices. Despite growing interest and efforts to transition to a more circular model, several systemic barriers remain, preventing stakeholders from fully realising the potential of the circular economy in the region. These challenges are multifaceted and stem from issues related to governance, collaboration, policy, infrastructure, and citizen engagement.

Below are the key challenges identified as also summarised in Figure 16.

²¹ COOPERATE Project. (n.d.). COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production: Call for champions, Annex I. Łódzkie region.

Figure 16: Key Challenges

Source: COOPERATE project.

1. Political instability

It was mentioned in the interviews that political shifts have disrupted regional-level support for circular initiatives. One example included the withdrawal of the regional government from a major international consortium following elections, citing changing political priorities and a lack of interest in continuing the project. This highlights the fragility of circular economy efforts that rely heavily on regional policy backing and underscores the need for resilient governance structures.

2. Public procurement barriers

Interviewees pointed out that public procurement procedures often prioritize the lowest-cost bids, which disadvantages circular solutions that may have higher upfront costs. This approach can hinder the adoption of more sustainable practices, even when they offer long-term economic and environmental benefits.

3. Weaker? stakeholder coordination

Although many stakeholders are open to collaboration, efforts remain fragmented and often project based. Interviewees described difficulties in aligning goals and establishing a unified approach, especially in the early stages of collaborative projects. The absence of structured, long-term partnerships slows progress toward systemic change. This lack of sustained cooperation across the region further hinders the ability to implement long-term solutions critical for the circular transition.

4. Lack of collaboration infrastructure

There is a notable lack of both digital and physical infrastructure to support ongoing collaboration among stakeholders. Many actors within the ecosystem do not have access to adequate tools for communication, data sharing, or joint planning, which limits their ability to work together efficiently. Interview feedback emphasized that the absence of essential IT tools is a significant barrier to sustaining ecosystem-wide initiatives, making it difficult to maintain long-term partnerships and share knowledge effectively across the region.

5. Limited civil society engagement

Citizen involvement in circular economy efforts remains relatively low in the Łódzkie region. While some initiatives, such as educational workshops, have been developed to raise awareness, they are still in the early stages and have not yet reached a broad audience or been scaled up. Interviewees stressed that greater public engagement is essential for driving the success of circular economy strategies, as behavioural change at the community level is a critical component of the transition to more sustainable, circular systems.

3.2.6 Priorities

A consistent theme across the interviews was the recognition that moving from isolated initiatives to a cohesive circular economy strategy requires more **structured and long-term collaboration**. Several interviewees emphasized the importance of creating institutional mechanisms, such as knowledge hubs, living labs, and circular economy incubators, that would enable stakeholders from various sectors (business, government, NGOs, and academia) to co-develop and scale circular solutions.

Technical and social innovations are both seen as crucial to advancing circularity in the region. Interviewees highlighted the development of pilot plants for processing organic waste as practical demonstrations of circular economy principles. These efforts aim to bridge the gap between theory and real-world implementation, offering tangible examples of circular systems in action.

Education was also highlighted as a key priority area in driving the circular economy forward. Interviewees emphasized their ongoing efforts to promote education at the municipal level, with the aim of cultivating a local culture of sustainability and circularity. This initiative focuses on empowering local communities to understand the importance of circular practices in their everyday lives. Similarly, further interviewees underlined the critical role of community engagement through educational activities. They stressed that by raising awareness about circular economy principles and practices, they can **inspire citizens to actively participate in and support the transition** to a more sustainable and circular society.

A key strategic focus is strengthening the existing relationships between universities, companies, and governments. Interviewees noted that the **lack of coordination among these actors is limiting the region's potential** in developing effective circular economy solutions. Although ad hoc collaborations already exist, often through EU-funded projects such as the FRONTSH1P project, there is a need for more permanent, trust-based partnerships. This was

echoed by further interviewees and reinforced by others, which highlighted the value of structured collaboration between NGOs and businesses.

Interviews also brought further insights into the role of large businesses in regional circular ecosystem. The FRONTSH1P project, involving 35 partners from 9 countries, includes systematic circular solutions developed across multiple material streams (e.g., plastics, water, wood). One example includes the use of wood pellets to heat production, capturing CO₂ and repurposing it for growing algae used in wastewater treatment, demonstrating circularity at an industrial scale. This work underscores the value of involving diverse regional and international partners and the **importance of clear communication and aligned incentives in collaborative projects.**

In conclusion, fostering a more cohesive and collaborative circular economy ecosystem in the Łódzkie region will require sustained effort across several fronts: scaling pilot projects, developing knowledge hubs, improving education and awareness, and forging long-term partnerships among key stakeholders. Successful models, like FRONTSH1P, can serve as concrete examples to inspire and guide future initiatives.

4. Conclusion

ERA Hubs present an opportunity for the pilot regions to structure their thinking and collaboration activities further, giving a name and further opportunity and space for the activities that can lead to further knowledge valorisation coming from the strengths of the region.

It is apparent that ecosystems require collaboration in order to fulfil their functions. Through the phase 1 and phase 2 piloting in COOPERATE, the applicability of the ERA Hubs definition has been tested across ecosystems and refined further to better match the ecosystem realities while at the same time propose a structure to further foster collaboration.

These use cases and case studies shed light on the way in which collaboration in ecosystems is structured towards knowledge valorisation, highlighting some challenges and priorities among them. Notable among them are the need for:

- governance mechanisms to foster collaboration,
- clear policy and strategy guidance and stability to enable ecosystems and value chains,
- access to innovation support and funding,
- weak collaboration with civil society
- public procurement barriers

The SELF-ASSESSMENT, the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX produced with the COOPERATE project present an opportunity for the pilot regions to further their development of their collaboration activities towards knowledge valorisation in their ecosystems around the studied use cases, and beyond. As self-identified emerging ecosystems, that are both moderate and emerging innovators according to the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), Centre-Val de Loire and Łódzkie region present R&I ecosystems that are on track to understand and tackle their specific challenges related to their use cases and develop these further within the ERA Hubs concept and support that has been offered to them.

These aspects are further discussed at the COOPERATE Co-creation session in May 2025, where the monitoring framework and policy recommendations together with the testing of the tools arising from COOPERATE including the SELF-ASSESSMENT, the PLAYBOOK and TOOLBOX, which were developed to assess and help progress the maturity of R&I ecosystems will be addressed.

5. Bibliography

AdvancedH2Valley (2024) AdvancedH2Valley: Showcasing Advanced Hydrogen Valley in Western France Retrieved from: <https://www.advancedh2valley.eu/>

Clean Hydrogen Partnership (n.d.) Hydrogen Valleys. Retrieved from: https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/get-involved/hydrogen-valleys_en

COOPERATE Project. (n.d.). COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production: Call for champions, Annex I. Centre-Val de Loire region.

COOPERATE Project. (n.d.). COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production: Call for champions, Annex I. Łódzkie region.

Dev'Up (2024) Power up with hydrogen in Centre-Val de Loire

Dev'Up. (2023). Centre-Val de Loire, a leading destination for businesses with foreign capital. Retrieved from: <https://www.devup-centrevaldeloire.fr/wp-content/uploads/foreign-investments.pdf>

Dev'Up. (n.d.). Investment in the Loire Valley. Retrieved from: <https://www.devup-centrevaldeloire.fr/invest-in-loire-valley-region/>

European Commission. (2023). Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2023 Regional Profiles France. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/assets/rtd/ris/2023/ec_rtd_ris-regional-profiles-france.pdf

European Commission. (2023). Regional Innovation Scoreboard. Retrieved from: <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris>

European Commission. (2024). Country Regional Profile: Łódzkie (PL71). European Union. Retrieved from: https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard/eis-2024#/ris/countries/PL?region=PL71&perf_indicators=1

European Commission. (n.d.) European Research Area Platform: Amplifying access to research and innovation excellence across the Union. Retrieved from: <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024/amplifying-access-research-and-innovation-excellence-across-union>

European Commission (n.d.) Hydrogen Valleys S3 Partnership. Retrieved from: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/policy/communities-and-networks/s3-community-of-practice/partnership_industrial_mod_hydrogen_valleys_en

FRONTSH1P. (2022). Policy Framework and Market analysis – POLICY.`

MINISTÈRE DE L'AMÉNAGEMENT DU TERRITOIRE ET DE LA DÉCENTRALISATION and MINISTÈRE DE LA TRANSITION ÉCOLOGIQUE, DE LA BIODIVERSITÉ, DE LA FORÊT, DE LA MER ET DE LA PÊCHE (2021) SRADDET: un schéma stratégique, prescriptif et intégrateur pour les regions. Retrieved from: <https://www.ecologie.gouv.fr/politiques-publiques/sraddet-schema-strategique-prescriptif-integrateur-regions>

Région Centre-Val de Loire (2020) Rapport du Président du Conseil Régional à la session Plénière du 18 février 2020 REGION 100% RENOUELABLE: UNE FEUILLE DE ROUTE POUR LE DÉVELOPPEMENT DE L'HYDROGÈNE VERT EN CENTRE-VAL DE LOIRE